

ROPES AND CABLES AS COMPOSITE LINEAR TENSILE MATERIALS

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Summary

The synthetic fiber ropes have in the past ten years advanced not only to the higher modulus Aramids, but to hybrid designs and composites. The bridging of the manufacturing monsters required for steel cables to the myriad of textile type machines processing the synthetic fibers has permitted both lower cost production and variations in design. The materials and the methods can be better tailored to the system requirements. Production runs, 100 km lengths, prototypes, and short runs are reproducibly made, or altered to meet new requirements. The properties and applications can cut across the steel and synthetics.

With this progress has come a complete revision and review of the almost decadent rope technology. Computer design, sophisticated testing and property measurement, composites technology, system analysis, and a better understanding of current rope and cable have all been necessary backgrounds for the incursion of the high modulus fiber into the old steel wire and synthetic rope markets. The elastomers and plastics have played special roles as impregnants, insulators, and jackets. Million pound ropes, umbilicals, and electromechanical cables are being made with KEVLAR^(R), as well as hundreds of smaller lines from 50 lb. test with 5 mil copper wires to 30,000 lb. break strength tethers with optic fibers. Low weight/high impact strength electrical cables are being made for space and military systems.

The newer high modulus fibers of Aramid, polyethylene, and refractories have come of age in ropes and cables, but the enhancement of these flexible linear tensile materials by the improvement of resin matrices and coatings has hardly begun.

(R) DuPont & Co. patented Aramid fiber.

The Oldest Man-Made Composites - Cables and Ropes

The field of composite materials and structures were born of high strength fibers and wires and encompasses the unique area of "linear tensile members", namely the cables and ropes. Pultruded rod and tube are the more conventional fiber-resin composites coiled in long lengths for tower guys and deep-well rods. But the Electro-Mechanical cables (E/M) and the ropes of wire or synthetic fibers are among the oldest and critical of structural members and composites.

You start your life supported by an umbilical, and may most likely exit lowered into a grave by a pair of ropes or slings. Meanwhile you travel on many systems that have ropes or cables as primary structures on elevators, bridges, tramways, and boats as well as cars and planes with their wires, cables, belts, and chains as secondary structures. The architect, engineer, farmer, fisherman, sailor, etc. take them as a matter of course, off-the-shelf, used and reused and hardly ever thrown away. But when a failure occurs, it is expensive and sometimes deadly. In our modern society you can rate the status of rope technology by the cost of casualty insurance, with product liability becoming prohibitive in cost and increasingly difficult to obtain. Too frequently the cables and ropes are afterthoughts purchased as accessories from a catalogue or the lowest bidder. They go by the sundry names of rope, wire, cable, line or chain; or cord, string, tie, and guy depending on the field of work. They are nevertheless critical elements in many system operations. Linear Tensile Members that may be cyclic and bending, static but never still, that have to be flexible, reliable and withstand extreme abuse.

Materials and Design in Rope Technology

Synthetic Ropes

The history of natural fibers converted to yarns for cloth and rope predates recorded history. Twisting the short fibers of cotton or flax and those native to each area created the yarns and continuity for weaving. The manual counterwisting to form the stranded cord and rope progressed over the millennia to small hand tools and to the rope-walks of the 18th century. Manila hemp became the best commercial fiber, while silk represented the highest quality with its continuous uniform filaments and high strength. The demands of ships and farms in the booming America of 1800 required almost two hundred rope-walks to serve the river and ocean traffic. The great sailing ships were rigged by the expanding giants of rope and chain, with huge stranding machines outmoding the miles of walks. A key feature of the rope makers art was his coating of resin or lubricant. To this day no fiber producer will tell you his secret surfactant, oil, binder or coating, but the common additives then were tallow, beeswax, whale oil, pine pitch, coal tar, and later petroleum tars and waxes. The natural petroleum crudes were mined for mortaring stone and impregnating rope centuries before the auto and fuel oil demands. The tars were the vital matrix that sealed the ropes and planking, and from which the sailors derived their fragrance.

The 3-Strand and the Braid or Plait were the basic rope designs and still are. It has taken centuries of ingenious mechanics to evolve the rotating high decibel machines that to this day

are the major mass manufacturing methods. World War II saw the last big surge in natural fiber rope production, and the advent of synthetics. Rayon became the first tonnage fiber for textile and tire cord, born and gone within my lifetime. Nylon has become a household word and dominates the plethora of synthetics. For ropes the hemp is still a major fiber, but far outclassed and outmoded by nylon and the poly-esters, ethylenes and propylenes. Now come the high modulus Aramids and ethylenes and the parade of high molecular weight chains while hemp, like leather and cork retain their special sectors of the market.

Impregnation of the yarn and rope with a flexible matrix remains amajor requirement for fatigue and abrasion resistance. The most effective methods now involve the continuous coating of the individual 10-20 micron size filaments as they are born from spinnerettes and dies. With the higher modulus glass and Aramids many tougher matrices are used by applying solvent base teraphthalates, urethanes, acrylates, etc. In addition outer skins or protective jackets are used that range from braided nylons and polyesters to extruded elastomers and compounds, and dip coatings, too numerous to detail. Each customer selects his rope or cable jacket according to his experience or chosen supplier, but it constitutes an important and expensive component.

With the continuous synthetic fiber the designer could select a fiber orientation to optimize properties. Figure 1 illustrates schematically the rope constructions. With electrical cores or outer helixed conductors they illustrate the electro-mechanical cable which is discussed in greater detail below. As background, the ancient but still common 3-strand rope offers the best compromise of high flexibility, low cost, and reasonable strength with great versatility in handling and termination. It does, however, produce torque under load, and it does not have the best strength-to-weight efficiency. With the exception of tire cord, the high modulus aramids should not be made as 3-strand ropes. The 3-strand design causes high internal radial compression that increases at higher tensile loads and with rope size. The tensile efficiency decreases from the 80-90% range under 1" to 2" diameter (20,000 to 90,000 lb. break strength) and tends to approach 60-70% of the potential total yarn strength. The break strength-to-weight is one measure of efficiency, illustrated in Table I, using data taken from commercial listings. As the sizes increase, the break strength decreases per unit weight and length. This represents 3-strand construction for the common materials, but the last column summarizes the advantage of an optimized design.

Table I. Trends in Tensile Break Strength per Pound of Rope

Rope Diameter	1/2"	1"	4"	Fig. 5
Polypropylene	89 *	78	69	120
Nylon	98	96	95	120
Polyester	80	72	65	105
Manila Hemp	32	30	22	
Kevlar (R)	260	234	(140-160)	360

*Break Str/lb/1000' for 3-strand ropes
(R) DuPont & Co. patented Aramid fiber

FIGURE 1. SCHEMATICS OF ROPE CONSTRUCTION

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BRAID / PLAIT

3-STRAND

WIRE-ROPE

COUNTER -

HELIX

C / H

FIGURE 2. LOAD vs ELONGATION

FIGURE 3. BREAK STRENGTH vs WEIGHT

Break strength test data on large ropes frequently shows a large scatter with 60% efficiency based on yarn strength. This is consistent also with the classical statistical predictions for multifilament structures that cannot redistribute stresses thru a continuous matrix.

Optimizing Design

Selecting the rope design based on application and fiber can improve the efficiency and rope properties, such as going to braid, parallel or counter-helix. A braid or plait has an equal number of strands woven into a left and right lay. This results in torque balance and retains good flexibility and fatigue resistance, particularly for low modulus synthetics. Based on the strength to diameter ratio, the packing factor for braid tends to be lower than 3-strand because it tends to form a hollow tube under tension, and it flattens to a ribbon over a sheave or drum. This behavior and the cross-over of the yarns internally can result in excessive abrasion at high loads. This is improved by adding a core such as twisted or parallel yarns, or a braid-over-braid. To retain good efficiency, however, the design must balance the elongations of the inner core and outer braid. The core can also be made the principal strength member, while the outer "tighter" braid has the dual role of strength member and protective jacket, plus color and size identification. Mountain climbing ropes represent among the most sophisticated of such designs. The braid angles (yarn to axis) are less critical for the high elongation synthetics like nylon, but are very critical for the Aramids as discussed below, with optimum strength at 10° to 15°.

An example of designing for minimum elongation and maximum strength-to-diameter is the use of parallel-lay, such as Nolaro by the Columbian Rope Co. Using polyester yarn for the core, drawn down as a tight bundle with back-tension and dies, the parallel fibers are encased in a tough extruded jacket of polyester or ethylene. With this construction, the strength to size efficiency is much better than 3-strand or braid. Figures 2 and 3 compare the efficiencies of the synthetics and different constructions. The parallel Nolaro has a lower elongation than the conventional polyester 3-strand rope (Fig. 2), approaching the Aramid. It is lower in unit weight than the 3-strand nylon in spite of its higher density (1.14 g/cc for Nylon and 1.42 for polyester). With this higher density, the overall rope diameter is smaller which is a significant factor in underwater towing and antenna tower guys because of the lower drag.

The High Modulus Aramid

When DuPont & Co. introduced KEVLAR (R) a new commercial high modulus fiber was available to compete with steel, without requiring the high capital investment for manufacturing galvanized wire rope. When marketed as a yarn in 1971, we at Cortland had already installed our first antenna guys (NSF/Cornell Radio-Astronomy Project at Arecibo, PR), using the pre-production PRD 49. This was a high strength (4-500,000 psi) high modulus (18-19 x 10⁶ psi) fiber that handled like nylon or polyester on braiders and textile machinery. In the intervening years we have had to learn how to adapt the manufacturing methods to the new material. The multitude of applications where KEVLAR competed with or replaced the stretchier synthetics and the heavier rusting steels

brought on an incredible number of system and materials design problems. The real challenge was to do all this at a profit and for many years DuPont classed Kevlar as an experimental fiber at \$7.50/lb. (1500 d. Kevlar 29 at 8×10^6 psi modulus). It is now at about \$11/lb. a commercial standard and Cortland has its ropes and cables on the Space Shuttle, in deep sea mooring, oil fields, the Arctics, and hundreds of systems around the world.

The high modulus Aramids have required both new designs and production methods. The parallel construction is satisfactory for very small diameter lines, such as used in reinforcing fiber optics filaments. This design is hopeless, however, for larger sizes of over a few thousand pound break strength because the filaments buckle when the rope is bent. Braiding at low angles is a very efficient option that can be used from 50 lb. to over 50,000 lb. BS but the splicing requirements pose problems for long lengths on larger sizes. The braider bobbins or reels have limited length capacities and splicing the strands becomes expensive and risky. The wire-rope construction is a good option for the larger sizes, and lends itself to a torque balanced design similar to double-armored steel cable with counter-helixed layers. The strand sizes and pitch for each layer have to be calculated and controlled for each size of cable, aided by the ever helpful computer. Since the cable contracts significantly under load, the torque balancing becomes difficult and really becomes only a method for minimizing torque at given load levels. In addition, one now has to contend with the predictable statistical distribution problem for the discreet number of strands, as in the 1 x 7 or 1 x 19 constructions, i.e. the close-packed configurations. As a result one can get occasional failures at 50% to 70% of design break strength. A major factor for these large cables is that the individual strands may have from 2000 to 30,000 lb. BS (1/8" to 5/8" d.) and there are no machines to apply the high proportional back-tensions to properly form the cables. They have far too much constructional stretch when first loaded, that is, taking the stretch out, and the strands can end up with different lengths. This is a principal cause for low break strengths in all large synthetic ropes.

A successful design for larger Aramid ropes and cables has been the wire - rope . A 1 x 19 torque balanced rope is an early version of this design, which would have an inner core of 6 strands with a left-lay over the center strand, and the outer 12 strands with a right hand lay. To maintain the torque balance, the amount of material in the outer strands relative to the core would be inversely proportional to the distance from the center. There are some good arguments for omitting the very center strand and using a dummy core of a polypropylene since it is difficult to match the strain to the helixed 6 strands around it. After many hundreds of tests with both Kevlar 49 and 29 cables we have found no evidence of either premature center strand failure or lower efficiency, i.e. the center strand can be properly designed to match the other 6 core strands. One can build this design up by both increasing the strand sizes, and by increasing the number of matched C/H layers. The cabling machines used can handle any strand length, avoiding splices, and 5000 to 20,000 ft. lengths have been made. There is trouble, however, with large strands over 1/4" dia. in getting a good packing and efficient strengths. While a wire rope is hard packed with preformed wires the Kevlar strands collapse inward under tension and increase

greatly the probability of non-uniform lengths and changing the torque balance. These strands can, however, be precoated either with the lubricating waxes applied by DuPont, or with other resins such as a urethane. Under load these resins act as a flexible matrix to minimize abrasion internally resulting from millions of cycles of tension-tension loading and vibration, or severe cycling over sheaves. In addition, tough polyester films of half or one mil Mylar can be wrapped between each counterhelixed layer. Marine tow systems, motion compensator cables on oil rigs balloon tethers (25,000 ft. long), sonobouy cables and antenna guys are examples of applications.

An alternative method of manufacturing with this C/H design has been to cable directly from the 10 or 20 lb. tubes of Kevlar yarn without the intermediate step of making strands. This was done originally to achieve very long splice free lengths of rope. What was found was that the individual tensioning of the smaller yarns as strands produced a much higher packing. A 30,000 lb BS cable that was a nominal 5/8" d. came out at under 1/2" d. Again the successive layers are layed at 10° to 15° to the axis with either decreasing angles at outer layers and/or changing the amount of Kevlar at each layer, alternating the layers left/right. This low angle offers high strength efficiency, low elongation, but permits easy bending without the local buckling of the parallel design, and retaining the high packing efficiency. There is little constructional stretch, retaining the torque balance with less of a diameter change. A significant factor here is the tighter jacketing that is retained after loading. The braided or extruded outer jacket will tend to sleeve or bunch up on sheaves or guides when the cable contracts under load leaving the jacket as a loose sleeve. The C/H design works very well with the electrical cables that may have single conductors or optic fibers or complex multiconductor cores.

Electro-Mechanical Cables and The High Impact Designs (HIP)

Even the simplest of instrument or communication cables that are to operate in protective conduits have frequently to survive temperature extremes, or moisture, or the stresses in deployment. The selection of the insulation is a complicated subject beyond the scope here but a few brief comments are in order. The polyethylene's are among the best and cheapest except over 80°C, improved by irradiation cross-linking. The flourinated hydrocarbon (TFE, FTP, Teflon, etc.) and the polyimides are the best for all extremes, short of ceramics. While good barriers against moisture, only the metal tubes are absolute. PVC insulation is very common, but for most all our applications we use the polyethylenes and polyolefin copolymers. As for stresses, the tensile loading problems are reliably handled by both steel wire and the Aramid. Severe compressive loading requires the steel armor and conduits. Impact loading, vibrations and cyclic tension through zero pose the most severe challenge with the mechanical failure of the copper wires. The solutions are not in the alloying of the copper or copper clad steel, but in the design of the conductors coupled with the insulation and strength member.

The down-hole logging cables used to lower instruments into deep oil wells are among the most sophisticated and successful for extremes of application. Frequently over 20,000 ft. in length,

they are made by completely integrated companies that can do all the operations from stranding the conductors to drawing and cabling with steel wire or alloys, all of superb quality and tolerances. The insulations run the gamut of all of the best and purest to withstand 10,000 psi hydrostatic testing, and retain the multi-gigaohm insulation resistance, routinely. For many reasons however, there are some applications that cannot use or afford these cables, although there are many variations made. Their design and quality nevertheless serve as a benchmark.

For the lighter weight requirements, or where non-metallic, non-magnetic properties are needed, the Aramid strength member offers a unique solution. Eventually the newer high molecular weight polyethylene fibers will offer some alternative modulus and density. The lower modulus synthetics cannot normally be used for the strength members because of the high elongations, but the Kevlar 29 with 5% to 6% elongation (at break) behaves quite well. At the normal working loads there is only 1% to 2% stretch depending on the construction and character of the electrical core. The low angle braid and C/H constructions are excellent for all sizes from #39AWG (5 mil) conductors with 50 lb BS braid to 1" d. multiconductor cores with 10,000 lb BS and higher braid or C/H Kevlar 29. With the conductors stranded or twisted these Electro-Mechanical cables (E/M) can take the tensile strain up to the breaking load of the Kevlar, including the 1/2% constructional or non-recoverable elongation. They can also withstand extensive tension cycling.

The following general guide lines must be followed for the conductor design: 1. Use the smallest conductors possible for the required power requirements of the system. 2. Use stranded wire only, not solid Cu, with #34 to #40 wires. 3. Use the maximum twist per inch both for the individual stranded conductors and for the bunching or assembly of insulated wires, i.e. cabling the core as ahelix. 4. Use the optimum geometrical pattern for packing the insulated wires, 6 around 1 or close packed hexagonal (1x7, 1x19, etc.) to form a round core. 5. Protect the core with extruded urethane jackets, or as a minimum tape wrapped Mylar. 6. Avoid designs with the strength member at the center which may under load deform or cut into the insulations.

Heavy cyclic loading over drums or sheaves will tend to compress and break up almost any type of jacketing. The use of properly grooved sheaves that support the cables and avoid excessive local deformation is extremely important. The sheave to cable diameter ratios must be as large as possible, never under 20/1 and preferably 40/1. Finally, the loads on the cables must not be over 20% of the break strength, and preferably 10% when many thousands of cycles over sheaves are involved. Conductor failure will occur sooner when these rules are not followed, which means that the system has to be designed in conjunction with the cable.

In situations where high impact loading, snap loading, or severe vibrations are expected, there are special conductor designs that have been derived. The worst case is the use of conductors within nylon ropes, such as for towing gliders. This has been solved by forming an elastic recoverable composite. One design for short lengths has been to helically wrap the conductors over a rubber core, such as surgical tubing. For long continuous lengths, Cortland has a design of high helix angle wires

over an elastic fiber core, finished with an outer extruded polyethylene insulation. The sizes and types of elastic core, conductors, and insulation are all selected according to the deployment problems which can vary from airplane towed magnetometers to missile launch systems, all subject to high shock loads. In addition to impact loads with cable elongations over 10%, these conductor designs survive extensive cycling.

A round conductor core cross-section is important for more than aesthetics but to permit a uniform loading or footprint under bending and cyclic loading, as well as the base for the strength member. Filler strands are commonly used in most cables to affect a round cross-section, packing the voids between conductors with cords, heavy yarns or monofilaments. It is also common practice to use water-blocking compounds in undersea cables. They displace the air between conductors and so retain a round cable cross-section under high hydrostatic loads. The major purpose is to minimize hosing or the incursion of water along the length of the conductor in the event of defects or leaks. Some of the materials used are polyethylene grease, petroleum jelly, and depolymerized rubber (DPR). They have to remain soft with a low shear strength and not form a stiff matrix. These compounds are expensive to apply, interfere with electrical termination, and are of doubtful value since the water will slowly diffuse along interfaces if there is a leak, but they have been an accepted practice for many years and carried along in military specifications. With modern extrusion practices and excellent quality resins both the conductor insulations and the outer jackets a far superior to those of ten or twenty years ago. The water-blocking is redundant and less of a necessity, in fact interfering with the final jacketing and termination. Most commercial underground cables now no longer require this added matrix.

The most recent inclusion of fiber optics in cables has required unique composite constructions. To minimize distortions and fractures (attenuation or loss of signal) the individual optic fibers are encapsulated either in a loose tube or coated with an acrylate. These jacketed single fibers are then further protected by extruding an elastomer jacket such as urethane reinforced with Kevlar 49 parallel strands. While this has considerably increased the diameter, these fibers can then be readily processed into cables or pulled thru conduits. There are as many designs as there are producers, which is now in the hundreds. A successful multifiber design forms a ribbon of 12 of the encapsulated or coated fibers and then stacks 12 of the ribbons to form a fiber/matrix of 144 elements over which a jacket is extruded. A recent successful test has been made on many continuous kilometers of underwater cable that uses a low angle twisted bundle of acrylate coated fibers encased in a thin wall brazed copper alloy tube. This is the only true barrier to moisture which degrades the fiber optics. The strength members on this design were a Kevlar 49 counterhelix. The greatest problem is a compressive loading such as a cross-over in winding on a drum, or crushing loads on a sheave or winch. This condition if not avoidable might work with a steel double armor. The thin walled sleeve of brazed copper or beam welded stainless certainly helps but that is not its main function. Incorporating the optic fiber within an electrical signal or power cable can be done, as long as the cabling and helixing process does not impose local distortions.

Failure, Testing, and Terminations

The unexpected failure of a rope or cable can be the result of 1. Underdesign or Overexpectation, 2. Abuse, or 3. Termination design or flaw. The first two items apply to any structure. The termination, or how one transmits the load at both ends, is similar to any joint or load transition point in a structure. Riveted, welded and brazed joints are common elementary topics in Strength of Materials, covered in detail by many analysis and specifications. The termination of ropes and cables, however, remains an art and is briefly reviewed below.

Expectations

Previous discussions have dealt with materials and design. Any relative evaluation, however, such as nylon vs. polyester, or Aramid vs. steel requires the specific details of the system and comparative testing. The project engineer and designer thinks in terms of safety factors of 2 or 3, but unless all conditions and loads are well known and controlled, this can be optimistic for ropes and cables. Standing or static lines, from past practice, require safety factors of 4 or 5 while running lines with dynamic loading conditions may need safety factors of 8 to 12. Excessive loads over small diameters wipes out these factors. The concentrated load or high stress point will tend to dramatically decrease the break strength and result in a large scatter of values obtained for strength and fatigue life.

The manufacturers have everything "on the line" and have to produce a uniform quality with a guaranteed break strength. Their sampling problem is difficult. A high degree of confidence is needed in the test methods. For a long continuous length of many miles, the rope is like the electrical conductor or insulation. One flaw anywhere in the thousands of feet of good rope leaves at best only short lengths. While testing for conductivity and continuity and resistance is quite exact, and done on any length of wire, the best one can do with rope is a proof loading at some high percentage of break strength. This is hardly practical for very long lengths. If the ropes are sold with an "average" strength, then the buyer has to add a margin. The designer must know and depend on a minimum break strength, and the manufacturer has to guarantee this even though he can only test samples periodically or from either end of a long line. His procedure for testing is therefore critical, as is his quality control, from yarn to packaging and shipping. This goes hand-in-hand with the termination used, as discussed below.

Use and Abuse

Like any structure, the rope and cable cannot be made idiot-proof, so there are a number of precautions and conditions to observe. The big claim for synthetics is the resistance to rot and mildew. They are, however, affected by a variety of acids and solvents as published by fiber suppliers, as well as ultraviolet and heat. Long term storage has to be done with care to avoid the aging and degradation. Over the past decade, the Aramid has proven itself extremely stable as far as shelf life. Protection from UV, sand and salt crystals are essential for the Aramid more so than the other synthetics. The classical example of poor practice is that of the most popular users of synthetics, namely

the yachtsmen and fishermen. Lines may be used from year to year not recognizing that they could be down to less than two-thirds their original strength. Even for the careful mountain climber we have tested lines that were down to 60% of rated strength although the exterior jackets did not show extensive wear. Mooring and dock lines can become dangerous, as are old ropes used by formers. While testing is not always possible, examination for broken strands, obvious fuzzing, or broken filaments inside the ropes can be done, plus a record or history. But who ever throws away a rope?

Two common problems are: 1. Redesigning or revamping a working system and using the same rope or cable, and 2. Using a system designed for another purpose. With the advent of the new high strength Aramids, there have been many attempts to use Kevlar where steel had served well. The need arises from new requirements to decrease weight or use a non-metallic rope. Too often the pulleys, sheaves, blocks, winches, etc. are not changed. Small diameters, flat rollers or wide grooves and low safety factors all conspire to grind the rope. The greatest problem is early success without knowing the margin of survival. Extensive cycling at loads over 10% to 15% of BS makes wear a serious problem, but at 40% to 50% of BS, the ropes may last only a few cycles. There is a threshold at which the Kevlar degrades very rapidly and comes apart. This applies to any of the synthetics, although nylon can withstand more abuse, and Aramid the least.

While the sheaves are rolling surfaces, the compressive failure is compounded on fixed surfaces such as chocks, bollards, cleats and stanchions. The sliding under high loads against the surface abraids, but also melts the synthetics. The higher temperature Aramid avoids the fusion, although manila can also withstand the high friction since it does not melt either. This form of failure also occurs when deploying at high loads off winches or reels. As the cable elongates at the tangent point it grinds away and destroys the jacket, abraiding internally as well. While the melted surface leaves an obvious mark of damage, the internal grinding can only be detected by unlaying the rope. The nearest approach to non-destructive testing would be to measure the elongation at about 40% of BS and compare it to the original properties. The older damaged rope or cable would behave like a lower BS line. Again the partial solution to better resistance comes with the fiber lube coating as a water insoluble matrix, and a tough impregnation of the special jacket such as a hard urethane. An open braided nylon with 50% coverage and a pressure extruded nylon like Zytel is about the best composite for abrasion resistance.

Terminations

The final step in a cable or rope assembly is the electrical connector and/or the load transfer fitting. Both power and communication requirements are well served by the manufacturers whose devices and techniques have to meet rigid military and government specifications. The laws and regulations that cover civilian and industrial electrical products are augmented by the severe requirements of reliable underwater connectors. The designs, testing and experience are well documented, a vital and profitable engineer controlled field. In contrast, the mechanical termination is a morass of do-it-yourself and patented gadgets

The list of knots, splices, grips and devices is endless. The success of the 3-strand rope, however, is in a large part due to the excellence of the splicing methods in terms of the high efficiency of the joint relative to the rope strength. Fishermen, sailors, and riggers have over the centuries devised many ingenious methods. These splices can be as high as 95% and repeatable by the trained technician. There are, however, no regulations, standards, or training comparable to the welder wherein certification is required for both different materials and methods. Instructions simply come with every package.

With small lines such as for fishing, some knots work quite well but extensive statistical testing shows a large distribution of break strength well below the potential 80-90%. For large ropes, knots result in 60% and less of rope BS. The problem is with the small turning radius and the compression generated with the tension. Synthetic fibers being highly oriented have very low compressive strength in the transverse direction. They flow and thin down. While Kevlar has a 4-500,000 psi tensile strength it has only about a 60,000 psi compressive tolerance. Similar to the mechanics of drawing a wire thru a die, the deformation of the fiber material occurs most readily when you combine a tensile load and radial compression. If the compressive gripping action is spread out over a longer length and larger area then the deformation decreases, and the efficiency of the grip, knot, or splice increases. It is the technique and art that results in a statistical spread of BS data as stress concentrations vary. The designer has to settle for the minimum break strength. The most efficient and consistent termination for most ropes and cables is the helical wrap or braid type, cruelly called Chinese finger or stopper and the patented versions PLP and Kellums. They are used by the hundreds of millions in the power and telephone industry. Notice the guys and connections on a telephone pole. The concept is the draw-down of a preformed helix on the rope or wire core. The key is that the core must be firm such as a pre-stressed rope, impregnated line, or steel rope.

The very tensile testing of ropes and cables is totally dependant on the pair of proper terminations. The fiber composites testing problems are similar except that most ropes and cables have no continuous matrix thru which to bond and transmit the load in shear. For yarns and small lines the counterpart to the composite ring test is a loop over large grooved capstans or drums. The metallurgist has a reliable solution for tensile testing by using a dumb-bell or dog-bone shape, machining the bar or plate so that the ends have about twice the cross-section area. The end taper or large fillet minimizes stress concentrations at the ends. Mechanical jaws bite into the heavy ends and these grips are gimbleled to permit good axial self alignment. The gage length is a standard 2" and very accurate elongations recorded while loading. For brittle materials, however, this art of testing is more difficult, but a disk, ring or bend test and hydrostatic tensile loading gives accurate and repeatable results. Sensitive samples like single crystals require a special art.

When a conventional v-grooved wedge grip such as used for steel bars is used for tensile testing wire on synthetic rope, a premature break occurs invariably at the jaws. There are patented modifications of this method (Lucker and Shaw/Electroline for example) which have greater success by more uniformly dist-

ributing the compressive load and translating by surface shear to the body of the rope. Forming an eye or loop and fastening with clips or clamps works well with steel wire rope if torque wrenches are used. Similarly, the swagged steel ring or pressed copper or nickel tube (Micropress) grips into the hard steel wire without compressive damage, but this is not a generally successful procedure with any synthetics unless very low loads are to be used and certainly not for a good tensile test to failure. Wedge/socket type fittings also tend to locally deform the fibers unless a collet type device is used like Electroline.

The forged steel socket or cone shapes with zinc (spelter) cast around the wires has been a standard for over 100 years, now at times modified by casting filled epoxies. Unless very carefully made and protected, however, the wires corrode at the nose of the sockets and high stress concentrations fracture the wires. The Roeblings used this method for all the bridge cables. Now after 100 years the Brooklyn Bridge cables are being resocketed, by essentially the same method. Swagged sockets were extensively tested some 40 years ago. The steel fitting deforms around the harder wire strands and if undamaged will result consistently in mid-span breaks which represents the 100% efficiency. Special swagging tools are needed, but these are available for field installation. The helical grip developed by PLP also has 100% efficiency, is the least expensive, and requires little tooling for field or lab application. It works well with steel and with an impregnated pre-stressed Aramid cable, but not the softer ropes.

The tucked eye splices that work so well for wire and synthetic ropes are not the best procedure for Aramid. Small braided Kevlar lines, however, can use the splice that tucks the end of the line back into the braid center to form an eye. Note that heavy forged thimbles have to be used with Aramid which have steel-like properties although they handle like other synthetics. These braid splices work like the Kellum's grip previously described and give the most reliable break strengths but not for large ropes over 10,000 lb BS. The epoxy/socket type is convenient but will give 80-90% efficiency. The Hood or counterhelical splice is by far the best for larger ropes of Aramid, again forming an eye with the Kellum's-type grip. These braid, socket, and Hood splices all lend themselves well to the electro-mechanical cables with the conductor pigtail brought out thru the eye, socket or sides. The preparation of any of these terminations must be treated in the same way as a welded joint. The technicians should pass quality control tests regularly. Note that any purely mechanical fitting will have a tendency to work loose in vibration and zero-load conditions. They depend on friction and tension closing the grip or braid so elastic adhesives or added fastening methods have to be included.

The most common procedure for both tensile testing and field use is the winding or warping on a large cylinder or capstan. Since this has both a sliding action and compression at the tangent point, the break will usually occur at or near the capstan. A half-hitch or cross-over will guarantee a lower BS. Knots in any form damage the Aramid fibers and the BS can be as low as 35%. Using high strength resins like epoxy to reenforce the termination causes high stress concentrations at the transition to the rope and special care is needed to avoid this.

Concluding Remarks

The High Modulus Fibers and their Composites offer the options of tailoring the materials to advanced design structures. For ropes and cables this has brought all the advantages of the composites. Electrical and thermal properties have been as important to space, surface, and undersea designs as the low weight and the high strength-modulus advantages, plus a chemical inertness heretofore unavailable. The corrosion problems of stainless and steel, the heat sensitivity of synthetics, lower dielectrics than glass without the embrittlement and water degradation - these all have assured a greater role for the Aramids and forthcoming high modulus fibers in the rope and cable technology. The enhancement of these flexible linear tensile members by the use of resin matrices has hardly begun. Just as the rope synthetics have been slave to the enormous textile industry, so the plastics for cores, jackets, and impregnants have been dependent on market availability. The billions of cycles on an instrument carriage drive, the thousands of miles of undersea cables, the safety of cable operated transportation systems, the extremes of space and military operations, will all be advanced by the new high modulus composite ropes and cables.